

ARTISTIC FEATURES OF EVELYN WAUGH

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ANNOTATION

Over the thousands of years during which satire has been derived from comedy, many different styles and tools have been used. Humor is one of the most effective, and therefore one of the most popular; some element of it is found in ancient Satire and nearly everywhere in modern Satire. This is perhaps most obvious in Evelyn Waugh's "A Handful of Dust", which never gives any overt indication of irony, but nevertheless the entire work is ironic. This style can also be seen in Evelyn Waugh's works. In "Decline and Fall" and "A Handful of Dust", the main characters always feel as though they are doing something wrong by violating the rules and values imposed on them y society, when in fact they are doing morally; a fact that is obvious to the audience but not to them.

Key words: *satiric tools, satirist, irony, genre, artistic features, English literature.*

Whichever tools a satirist uses to create his or her work, *satire* is one of the most effective and successful ways of getting a message out in the world, even in current period. The genre shows no signs of stopping, or even slowing down. Focusing on this tradition, we analyzed Evelyn Waugh's satirical works. While analyzing the author's works we improve our knowledge on English Literature.

First of all, there are not as many as frameworks which focus on *satire* as a new genre of literature. That's why we began with its etymology, then we moved its elements, methods as well as its nature. Secondly, while investigating we dealt with also the works of satirists who contemporary to Evelyn Waugh. We analyzed Ronald Firbank, Aldoux Huxley, Norman Douglas, Nancy Mitford's works. As a matter of fact, all satirists of that time show their attitude to the period as well as society throughout their works. Therefore, their works cover the time and real people who are aimless and weak. It should be noted that all works appeared between the World War I and the World War II. Maybe because of it society is unhappy and aimless. That's why satirists draw the picture of that time as ironically and comically.

While analyzing Evelyn Waugh's satirical works it is obvious that his works look like his contemporaries. He writes about real events, real people. Thus, he mocks

at them, he tries to demonstrate their faults. While reading his books, one can read them without stopping because the fortune of his characters is scintillating.

Professor Megan LeBoeuf puts forward this statement in his article: “Lamachos’ arguments for war might be equally as compelling as Dikaiopolis’ arguments for peace; certainly the rhetoric he uses in the play would have been commonly used by politicians of the day, and is still used even today by modern politicians. What matters in the end is that peace is demonstrated to be beneficial, and war to be detrimental to the individual”[1].

We agree to his statement that peace is beneficial while war is harmful. So, it proves that the author’s outlook and dexterity is great. He puts forward the main problem of society which is an essential one nowadays.

Besides, that Aristophanes utilizes the names of well-known people for making fun. Dikaiopolis’s speech illustrates it: “I know him. It’s limp-wrist Kleisthenes, the All-Athenian Boy!”[2].

On the one hand such sentences have a comic sense, on the other hand they can be a tool of critique and social commentary. While analyzing, one can come across its elements. As a matter of fact, his followers also utilize the elements of social commentary. One can notice such elements in Evelyn Waugh’s “*Put Out More Flags*”. This novel is in term of war, as Aristophanes “*Acharnians*”. It depicts generation during the early years of the World War II. The novel starts in Autumn 1939 with the beginning of the World War II and ends in Summer 1940 with the fall of France and from this time the war becomes serious for Britain, as it should fight for existence otherwise, it can lose its century’s old independence. The novel brings out British unpreparedness and mismanagement during the war. Evelyn Waugh describes Basil Seal (character of “*Put Out More Flags*”) as regardless being a hero in the novel, the author mocks at his actions. He is given a portrait of embarrassment to his mother as well as to his sister and her husband: “*Basil from his earliest days had been a source of embarrassment and reproach*”[2;14].

The author satirically portrays Basil’s qualities through his mother’s wishes: “*...Basil, her wayward and graceless and grossly disappointing Basil, whose unaccountable taste for low company had led him into so many vexatious scrapes in the last ten years, whose wild oats refused to correspond with those of his Uncle Edward; Basil who had stolen her emeralds and made Mrs. Lyne distressingly conspicuous; Basil, his peculiarities merged in the manhood of England, at last was entering on his inheritance*” [2;28].

In addition to this all women characters comprising Basil’s mother, his sister and his mistress wished him to die as a hero, after the shameful life he had lived: “*Nonsense, Jo. Men of forty-five and fifty enlisted in the ranks in the last war and died*

as gallantly as anyone else. Now I want you to see the Lieutenant-Colonels of the foot guard regiments and see where he will fit in best...” [2;23]. In this case, Evelyn Waugh satirizes mothers of that time. Mothers never want their children to die before them. They grow up their off-springs at the heart, they wish they have a long life and the best destiny. Besides that, in this novel the author mocks at human corruption. He portrays this problem in the conversation, held between Colonel Plum (character of *“Put Our More Flags”*) and Basil Seal, demonstrating Basil’s attitude to taking part in the war not for his obligation but for getting a job in the army:

“-As it happens,’ said Basil with dignity, ‘I came here to serve my country. I don’t particularly want money”.

-“The devil you don’t? What do you want then? You can have Susie. I had the hell of a fight to get her away from the old brute in charge of pensions”.

-“We can fight that out later. What I really want most at the moment is a uniform”[2;149].

Besides that, the novel also mocks at the people who are running away from England when it is in a dangerous situation. On the one hand, it happens because of dislike for foreigners in other words, it is xenophobia whileas the country is fighting for its dignity and prestige, on the other hand, some of them as Parsnip (character of *“Put Out More Flags”*) and Pimpernell (character of *“Put Out More Flags”*) are leaving their country in order to search for a new safe place to save their lives:

“What I don’t see is how these two can claim to be Contemporary if they run away from the biggest event in contemporary history. They were contemporary enough about Spain when no one threatened to come and bomb them”[16;89].

Later satirizing Parsnip and Pimpernell, the author makes them look very unimportant when he depicts Tom (character of *“Put Out More Flags”*) who is conscientious enough to admit that he had no conscience. As a matter of fact we can say, the author’s method of writing is to put very low morals and very high morals together: *“There was a young man of military age in the studio; he was due to be called up in the near future. ‘I don’t know what to do about it,’ he said. ‘Of course, I could always plead conscientious objections, but I haven’t got a conscience. It would be a denial of everything we’ve stood for if I said I had a conscience”[2;42].*

The writer demonstrates his characters’ unconscious position very well. While analyzing his writing style one can notice his great satirical method:

“-No, Tom,’ they said to comfort him. ‘We know you haven’t a conscience.

-But then,’ said the perplexed young man, ‘if I haven’t got a conscience, why in Gods name should I mind so much saying that I have?”[2;42].

Additionally, the narrator satirizes the aimlessness of the society in various ways. By describing the scene after a party, the author claims that the complete younger generation was aimless where nobody knows why, where and with whom to go:

“The party left the restaurant and stood in an untidy group on the pavement, unable to make up their minds who was going with whom, in what direction, for what purpose”[3;61].

As a matter of fact, the author wants to show that everybody should have aims to live in the world. So, the author mocks at the modern generation for their aimlessness and criticizes the society in general for being egoist and thinking more about themselves than their country at the essential time of the war. With the progress of the novel the writer portrays his another character, Alastair, unlike Peter Pastmaster and Basil Seal, who joins the army not for his personal benefits but to serve his country, to do his best, as he feels guilty enjoying his day while his country is at war. While demonstrating their position, he writes all sentences with the whole heart as well as he uses the elements of comic and irony. The author depicts Alastair thinking: *“It came as a shock to him now to find his country at war and himself in Pyjamas, spending his normal Sunday noon with a jug of Black Velvet and some chance visitors. Peter’s uniform added his uneasiness. It was as though he had been taken in adultery at Christmas or found in mid-June on the steps of Bratts in a soft hat”*[4;45].

Furthermore, the novel explores the hypocrisy and superficial attitude of aristocratic society, which has the similar attitude looking identical at each other. Waugh depicts the commonness of the girls in the upper-class society, one of which Peter was supposed to marry. Thus, due to their commonness he often fails to find any difference between them and sometimes he calls them with wrong names: *“He really could see very little difference between the three girls; in fact he sometimes caused offence by addressing them absentmindedly by the wrong names. None of them carried a pound of superfluous flesh; they all had an enthusiasm for the works of Mr Ernest Hemingway; all had pet dogs of rather similar peculiarities. They had all found that the way to keep Peter amused was to get him to brag about his past iniquities”* [4;152].

Besides that, the author portrays the real history throughout his novel. Waugh also satirizes the British army, its mismanagement and shows that there is no discipline:

“At this moment, just as the men were beginning to settle down, Captain Mayfield appeared. ‘Where the hell are those platoon commanders?’ he asked. ‘And what is the company doing here? I said the B in Bee, this is the E in Garden’[5;130].

We can conclude that Evelyn Waugh draws the picture of the British army unprepared for the war. The author wants to say people like Basil, Peter and Mr. Bentley can attain success, whereas honest people like Mr. Rampole and Lady Seal just turn out to be victims of modern generation, because their values and morals are

not valued any more. So, while mocking at such people, the author also wants them to be attentive towards their duties. He also says that the modern generation needs to be led in a proper way, otherwise with the wrong ideals and morals they will fail and follow the path of destruction. Therefore, all they can do is to put more flags in order to show their dignity and prestige.

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